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Abstract

This multiple case study explored the views and insights of Teachers who use Youtube videos in their class. The researcher formulated questions to collect data which was followed by the analysis of results. This research can be an avenue to discover the emerging revelations of teachers in their use of Youtube videos. The study employed the qualitative analysis using the multiple case study method. The participants were identified through purposive sampling. There were 3 participants which served as the primary source of data. The researcher interviewed the participants and the data gathered was generated through a semi-structured interview using validated interview questions as instruments. Transcripts of interviews were analyzed through thematic analysis. The result revealed that participants embraced the differences of their perspective to cope with their experiences. The themes that were generated are the following themes: Improvement, Easy access, Abundance of resource, Supplement, Appropriate, Interest, Time Frame and Familiarity, Motivation and Active learning.

1. Introduction

Founded in 2005, YouTube has quickly become a leader in online media. YouTube is an Internet application in which people can upload, share, and watch videos. There are millions of messages being uploaded each day onto this forum. Empirical evidence shows that Youtube is contribute to the wholistic learning of students. Thus, this research is an avenue to discover the emerging ideas that stem from the perspective of teachers. Teachers are the frontliners of education and it is their task to facilitate the learning of their respective students. This study will be a significant endeavor in the lens of teachers on expressing their insights on the use of Youtube videos in the classroom. In addition, this will be valuable to the stakeholders of the institution who will be enlightened by the output that will be brought about by the research. Finally, it will be helpful to future researchers who wish to explore further a similar scope to this study.

2. Literature Review

Creative teaching strategies that incorporate innovative technology motivate and engage learners who are technology savvy and are accustomed to the online environment. Using a variety of instructional methods and learning activities in the classroom creates an enriched learning environment for the student (Beldarrain, 2006). Using videos is a creative strategy. It was explored by Pappas (2016) that videos found

in YouTube can also be an indispensable learning tool that eLearning professionals can use to make their eLearning courses more enjoyable. In a separate study of Dowse (2009) discovered that YouTube videos provide a wide variety of content suitable for English teaching. There have been other explorations of how YouTube can be used in the classroom setting. It can be used to develop writing skills (Barbeau,2010), and it is used to make teaching engaging and interactive to students (Brandejs, 2016).

3. Methodology

This work adopted a qualitative study employing a case study because it seeks to explore the similarities and differences of teachers using Youtube videos in the classroom setting. This investigation is multiple case study which permitted the researcher to uncover the comparative cases and what are distinct (Yin,2013). Furthermore, a multiple case study empowers the researcher to break down each setting and across settings (Baxter & Jack,2008). It is also a variation that presents at least two or more interpretations and findings of a similar phenomenon (Santos & Eisenhardt, 2005).

The investigation involved 3 participants, whose backgrounds were based on their age, experiences and number of years in service. It was emphasized that this design would look into the multiple perspectives of the situation and make generalizations of what something is like. This depends primarily on the data gathered from the interviews with carefully participants (Raagas,2010) Moreover, the researcher's concern was on the participant's experience and how it varies from the others. (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

This study focused on the participants experience in the use of Youtube videos in the classroom setting. I noted down the participants' comments and behavior during the course of the study and to further add to the data. Further readings from other researches were used to enrich the analysis drawn from the data gathered.

4. Results and Discussion

Teachers are the heroes of the educational system. These teachers propel their students to different heights; protect the students from mediocrity and save the students from stagnancy. These characteristics are both manifested by heroes and teachers which bridges the common ground that teachers and super heroes are the same. The three superheroes are all members of one super hero team the Justice league like the three participants who belong to one institution.

4.1Case 1 - Superman. Superman is a college professor handling English subjects. He has been teaching in college for 10 years. Superman was given such a pseudonym because among the three participants, he is the one who has attained success in his teaching career. He has also earned his doctorate degree and, just like Superman who is above all things in Justice League.

Superman's experiences in the use of Youtube videos in the classroom can be summed up into; Improvement and Easy Access. He believes that using YouTube videos in the classroom helps his students improve in the learning outcomes of the subjects he is handling. He has observed the difference of the knowledge of his students from before and after the course. He believes that one of factors that caused this

change is by integrating Youtube videos in the classroom setting. Furthermore, He did not encounter many difficulties in using Youtube videos because the videos are readily available and provides Easy Access. He mentions that the website can be accessed by anyone who has internet connection.

Superman's considers the following criteria in selecting Youtube videos; Appropriateness and Interest. Superman carefully selects the videos he uses in the classroom setting so that it is appropriate to the level of competency of his students. He also adds that aside from the appropriateness, Interest is another consideration when he selects videos for classroom use. He believes if the video is interesting then it allows the students to participate better in the classroom discussion.

Superman's main insight in using videos is Motivation. He mentions that "Youtube videos can be used to motivate students in the classroom. If done exceptionally well, students will surely perform better."

Case 2 – Batman – Batman is a college professor handling English subjects. He has been teaching in college for 5 years. Batman was given the pseudonym because among the three participants, he is the one who technologically literate. The participant himself even expressed that he is up to date with technology. He is likened to Batman who is most technologically literate of three superheroes; Superman, Batman and Wonderwoman.

Batman's experiences in using Youtube videos can be encapsulated into; Improvement, Abundance and Supplement. Batman believes that using Youtube videos can help improve the student's competencies if used effectively. Batman also mentioned that Youtube videos offer an abundant resource that range from educational videos, movies and more. Finally, Batman also asserts that Youtube videos can serve as a supplemental to help better understand topics that are abstract.

Batman believes that careful consideration to Appropriateness, Interest, Timeframe and Familiarity are the essentials for the use of Youtube videos in the classroom. Appropriate videos that are suited to the topics would help the students better understand the topic discussed. Interest is also an integral factor because this would capture the attention of the student. Furthermore, Timeframe becomes a contributing factor to the student's success rate in learning because the length of the video can be a determinant of the student's attention in class. Batman also observes familiarity. Students who are familiar with the Youtube videos find it easier to connect the ideas with the subject matter.

The main insights that Batman shared are Motivation and Active learning. Batman strongly supports that if Youtube videos are highly motivating it would have lasting effects on the students. In addition, Youtube videos can induce the learners to be actively participate in class.

Case 3 – WonderWoman – Wonderwoman is college professor who teaches English. She has been teaching in college for 3 years. Wonderwoman was given the pseudonym because, she is the only woman from the three participants.

Wonderwoman's experience with the use of Youtube videos is mainly characterized into Improvement and Abundance. Wonder woman has observed the improvement of her students when she integrated the use of Youtube videos in her class. She noticed that students in her class have improved scores. She also observed that Youtube has abundant resources. The resources are vast and there are also videos devoted to

expanding topics that are discussed in the classroom setting.

Wonderwoman considers the Appropriateness and the Time frame when she selects Youtube videos. She carefully considers if the Youtube videos she uses in her classes fit her students. She has experience in the past that if the videos utilized are not fitted to the students there was a negative effect on the students. Timeframe is another criterion that she also carefully considers. She carefully analyzes the length of the video whether it can be integrated in her lesson design. She mentions that Careful attention to time should be taken so that videos can be used properly in class.

Wonderman’s main insight is the Active learning of the students. If Youtube videos are used effectively this enables the students to be active in class. Wonderman observed that students participate more and perform better in class. In the words of Wonderwoman, Students are active in learning.

Table 1. Themes and Core Ideas on the experiences of teachers using Youtube Videos

Emerging Themes	Core Ideas
Improvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students improve in the learning outcomes. • Improve the student’s competencies if used effectively. • Improvement of her students when she integrated the use of Youtube videos
Easy Access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The website can be accessed by anyone who has internet connection
Abundance of Resource	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Youtube videos offer an abundant resource that range from educational videos, movies and more • The resources are vast and there are also videos devoted to expanding topic
Supplement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Youtube videos can serve as a supplemental to help better understand topics that are abstract.

Presented in table 1, each teacher had different ideas to share in their experience of using Youtube Videos. The participants of this study revealed key points in their experience. There were some distinctions but also similarities.

In this study, I have observed that these teachers are firm believers that using Youtube videos in classroom improves the students. Similar results were drawn from a study that went through the method of using songs in YouTube to improve vocabulary competence. (Abidin et. al, 2011). Another study drew similar results through anchoring instruction on videos (Barron 1989)A study conducted by Kasper (1997) illustrated that teaching English using multimediaincreased the reading and writing examinations of students.

Considering the unique case of Superman, who was the only participant to assert the Easy Access

of Youtube. He did not encounter many difficulties in using Youtube videos because the videos are readily available. YouTube has offered a new way of accessing to a rank of information and video resources in a simple way, which does not require any special skills and is free (Snelson& Perkins,2009).Another Unique case was drawn from the statement of Batman. He mentioned that Youtube videos can Supplement learning. Such statements were confirmed that vidoes can clarify comprehension,consolidate concepts and reinforce learning (Singer,1997).

Two of the participants made mention of Youtubes having Abundance of resource. This was confirmed in a study that showed YouTube as an infinite resource for language learning because it provides learners with various language sources such as songs, music videos, movie trailers, talk shows, lectures, debates, and parodies (Balcikanli, 2011)

Table 2. Themes and Core Ideas on the factors Teachers consider in selecting Youtube Videos

Emerging Themes	Core Ideas
Appropriate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appropriate to the level of competency of his students. • Appropriate videos that are suited to the topics would help the students better understand the topic discussed. • If the videos utilized are not fitted to the students there was a negative effect on the students.
Interesting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the video is interesting then it allows the students to participate better in the classroom discussion. • Interest is also an integral factor because this would capture the attention of the student.
Time Frame	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The length of the video can be a determinant of the student’s attention in class. • The length of the video can be analyzed whether it can be integrated in her lesson design.
Familiarity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students who are familiar with the Youtube videos find it easier to connect the ideas with the subject matter..

Reflected in table 2, choosing which Youtube videos to use in the classroom setting is not by random. The Participants have a set of criteria that are considered whether the Youtube video is applicable to the

class. This shows that even if the criteria may vary there is a systematic set of norms that teachers abide before deciding to use a Youtube video in the classroom

In this study, I was able to discover 4 themes; Appropriate, Interest, Time Frame and Familiarity. All the Participants share the same ideology of using Youtube videos that are appropriate. This was confirmed by a study which revealed that Content should be age- and skill-appropriate, as “the content one watches may be a truer determinant of future academic success (CPB,2008) Furthermore, choosing what is appropriate for the students plays a pivotal role in teaching because it dictates the ways in which individuals take in information (Marshall ,2002).

However, in terms of Interest, only Superman and Batman share the idea. A study highlights the great advantage of the digital video technology as it matches in the best way with the students’ interests (Shrosbree,2008). On the other hand, only Batman and Wonderman hold that Time Frame should be taken into consideration. Language teachers should also consider the time frame of utilizing videos. A study suggested that video should be shown in short periods as opposed to showing a full feature-length movie without intermediate comprehension activities. With a 15-minute time limit(Canning,2000).

From the three participants, only Batman had an isolated case of Familiarity as an item to consider in selecting videos. He believed that a degree of familiarity helps students bridge the gap towards abstracts ideas. An idea which was explored in the study of Fleck et al., (2013), the research suggested that the more familiar students are with online learning tools, the more willing they are to use them in the class.

5. Conclusion

On the ideas that were shared by the participants, it can be implied that in teaching Youtube videos play a pivotal role. These videos breath some refreshing light onto the stale teaching methods that are employed by teachers. Regardless if the subject matter maybe different, Using Youtube videos helps students. The results of these experience of the teachers would show that Videos belong in the academe. It is a matter of choosing the right videos for the right subject matter.

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